

1 **Multi-use of the sea: a wide array of opportunities from site-**
2 **specific cases across Europe**

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23

24 **Abstract**

25 The concept of multi-use of the sea has gained popularity in the last decades with ocean space getting
26 increasingly crowded due to the development of the maritime economy, particularly in coastal areas and
27 in regions with relatively small sea space. This concept is based on the idea that competing claims for
28 space can be a source of conflict but may also lead to mutual benefits for the different users when
29 sustainable combinations are sought. Despite increasing European-wide efforts, on-the-ground
30 knowledge and practice of multi-use are still limited. With the aim to investigate opportunities for multi-
31 use development in the European seas, 10 case studies were selected from different site-specific contexts.
32 This paper analyses characteristics and the potential for ocean multi-use development by integrating
33 outcomes from desk analysis and perceptions of stakeholders from different action arenas in each of the
34 case study locations. Commonalities and contrasts amongst different combinations of sea uses are
35 discussed. The results show a high heterogeneity of multi-use opportunities across cases, with many
36 different combinations identified. The examined cases shared an overall balance between factors
37 promoting (drivers) and hindering (barriers) multi-use development, and the prevalence in stakeholders'
38 opinion of expected benefits (added values) of multi-use implementation on its possible negative impacts.
39 Actions required at local, regional (sub-national), and national levels to further exploit multi-use potential
40 are proposed.

41

42 **Key Words:**

43 Multi-Use; marine management; maritime economy; Blue Growth; maritime spatial planning; synergies;
44 coexistence; co-location; marine renewables; coastal tourism, stakeholder engagement.

451 Introduction

46An ever increasing variety of commercial activities exist in European sea basins: oil and gas (O&G)
47extraction; renewable energy production; pipelines and cables; shipping; coastal and maritime tourism;
48fisheries; aquaculture and blue biotechnology; sand and mineral extraction. Furthermore, the sea offers
49several intangible assets linked to the cultural and natural capital that it hosts, and also different services
50related to e.g. marine defence and oceanographic monitoring and research. To that end, under Blue
51Growth [1], [2] concepts and approaches, maritime activities are expected to grow in the near future,
52which may intensify conflicts, particularly in cases where different uses compete for the same space.

53In order to increase efficiency in the use of ocean space and build synergies among sectors, uses should
54be concentrated wherever possible. Towards this objective, the concept of Multi-Use (MU) of the oceans/
55seas aims not only to mitigate conflicts, but also to strengthen mutual advantages between specific uses;
56this approach would lead to minimising the use and the cost of resources, including space, and potentially
57reduce environmental impacts in specific maritime locations. However, there is still relatively little
58experience on how to integrate multiple uses and functions that share the same space at sea. Given the
59heterogeneity of uses involved, the challenge is to find compatible economic activities and to explore
60combinations between maritime sectors and uses related to the protection of natural and underwater
61cultural resources [3].

62The concept of MU of the sea has already been discussed for almost two decades, e.g. combining
63offshore wind energy (OWE) with aquaculture in the North Sea [4], [5], [6]. This combination was
64recently considered relevant for global food production, trade, electricity, and its powerful social and
65ethical implications [7]. Several other examples of MU have also been studied in recent years, including:
66OWE and environmental protection in coastal waters [8]; OWE and wave energy production [9];
67fisheries and tourism (also referred as pescatourism) [10].

68In 2010 the ‘The Ocean of Tomorrow’ cross-thematic calls under the European Union (EU) Research
69Framework Programme FP7 were launched with the intention of fostering multidisciplinary approaches

70on key cross-cutting marine and maritime challenges. Opportunities to explore MU platforms were
71created and they were exploited by three main projects: MERMAID (Innovative Multi-purpose offshore
72platforms: planning, design and operation, [11], [12], [13]), TROPOS (Modular Multi-use Deep Water
73Offshore Platform Harnessing and Servicing Mediterranean, Subtropical and Tropical Marine and
74Maritime Resources) and H2Oceans (Development of a wind-wave power open sea platform equipped
75for hydrogen generation with support for multiple users of energy). These experiences—all foreseeing
76the realization of engineering infrastructures at sea (defined here as *hard* uses)—evaluated in detail the
77technical and economic implication of feasibility.

78Despite these research initiatives, a broader analysis of opportunities and barriers for the realization of
79multi-use platforms and implementation of MU in general is still lacking: in order to advance MU real
80commercial practice, a clear understanding of challenges related to policy, authorization procedures,
81safety issues, investments, cross-sector dialogue, societal acceptance and other key factors is crucial.
82This article aims to contribute to this topic by assessing MU at local levels in 10 different case studies,
83exploring the variety of MU experiences and possibilities across different European locations. The
84objective is to provide knowledge on which specific MU combinations have greater opportunity to be
85developed or strengthened and which are seen as more beneficial for the environmental-socio-economic
86context at a local level. The paper also aims to provide a more general understanding on what types of
87MU are considered as more promising across European seas and what maritime activities could drive
88MU development in local contexts. Finally, the paper aims to identify key actions to be undertaken to
89practically promote MU development.

90Given these objectives, the Research Issues (RIs) addressed through this study are:

- 91 - RI-1. identification of the most suitable MU combinations in local contexts throughout Europe
- 92 - RI-2. evaluation of MU potential and MU overall effect on the environmental-socio-economic
- 93 system, including identification of relevant factors for MU development (e.g. drivers and barriers
- 94 to MU, expected benefits and negative impacts of MU)

- 95 - RI-3. identification of commonalities and contrasts amongst different combinations, groups of
96 combinations and different local contexts
- 97 - RI-4. identification of actions needed to support MU development, emerging from the site-
98 specific contexts.

99 Site-specific and concrete aspects from a selection of local contexts (case studies) were investigated, also
100 taking into consideration the perspective of local actors. By integrating results from the different cases,
101 we were able to develop a structured base of qualitative and quantitative data, and to analyse commonalities
102 and contrasts across cases, combinations and different categories of MU, thus providing a better
103 understanding of the real needs for MU implementation in local contexts.

104

105 **2 Methods**

106 In order to tackle RIs, a methodology was defined combining desk analysis with stakeholder engagement.
107 This allowed the exploitation of already available, documented knowledge and data, as well as the
108 collection of undocumented knowledge and perceptions, and most recent information from stakeholders.
109 Due to the nature of RIs considered, we introduced in the analysis both qualitative elements (e.g. factors
110 influencing MU development) and quantitative indicators (estimation of MU Potential and MU Effect, as
111 defined below).

112 The following definitions were adopted:

- 113 - MU = “In the realm of marine resource utilisation, multi-use should be understood as the joint use
114 of resources in close geographic proximity. This can involve either a single user (one operator
115 running two or more activities in the same location, e.g. an energy developer installing a OWE /
116 wave hybrid platform) or multiple users (two or more distinct operators performing different
117 activities in the same location, e.g. one OWE operator and one aquaculture operator). MU is an
118 umbrella term that covers a multitude of use combinations in the marine realm and represents a

119 radical change from the concept of exclusive resource rights to the inclusive sharing of resources
120 by one or more users" [14]

121 - Drivers = factors promoting or strengthening the development of MU

122 - Added values = positive impacts of establishing or strengthening MU

123 - Barriers = factors hindering the development of MU

124 - Impacts = negative impacts of establishing or strengthening MU.

125

126**2.1 Case study selection**

127In order to assess the most suitable MU combinations for different specific contexts around Europe, and
128collect information on factors influencing MU and recommendations for facilitating its development, ten
129case studies were selected (Fig. 1).

130

131

132**Fig. 1 Geographical location of the 10 case studies (background map from ©OpenStreetMap**
 133**contributors, ©CARTO). Legend:** Case study 1: MU between commercial fisheries and offshore wind
 134energy production in the UK (Scotland, North Sea) [15]; Case study 2: MU between tidal energy
 135development and environmental protection and monitoring in the UK (Scotland, North Sea) [16], [17];
 136Case study 3: MU between offshore wind energy production and aquaculture and fisheries in Germany
 137(German EEZ, North Sea) [18]; Case study 4: MU between marine renewable energy production and
 138aquaculture in the UK, including the use of renewable near the point of generation (Scotland, Atlantic
 139Ocean) [19]; Case study 5: MU between tourism and fisheries in Portugal (Algarve region, Atlantic
 140Ocean) [20]; Case study 6: MU between tourism and fisheries in Portugal (Azores, Atlantic Ocean) [21];
 141Case study 7: MU between wind energy production, tourism and environmental protection in Sweden
 142(Baltic Sea) [22]; Case study 8: MU between wind energy production and mariculture in Denmark
 143(Baltic Sea) [23]; Case study 9: MU driven by tourism and O&G decommissioning in Italy (Northern
 144Adriatic Sea) [24]; Case study 10: MU driven by marine renewable energy production in Greece (Aegean
 145Sea) [25].

146

147For the selection of the case studies, the following criteria were considered:

- 148 – Geographical representativeness of EU seas (Eastern Atlantic, North Sea, Baltic Sea,
 149 Mediterranean Sea)
- 150 – Offshore and nearshore activities representativeness (considering nearshore about < 12 nm and
 151 offshore about > 12 nm)
- 152 – Coverage of different sectors of the blue economy

153 – Consideration of both “hard uses of the sea” (relying on industrial and engineering infrastructures,
154 such as renewable energy production) and “soft uses of the sea” (uses involving no or limited
155 infrastructures, such as small-scale fisheries)
156 – Representativeness of different levels of MSP process maturity
157 – Representativeness of both already implemented and of potential cases of MU.
158 Selecting these cases we considered MUs that have been explored to some extent through pilots, as
159 well as innovative combinations of emerging and traditional maritime uses. We also included less
160 visible MUs but playing a significant role in coastal communities. On the whole, a wide variety of
161 environmental and socio-economic conditions, as well as of policy, research and technology
162 development contexts were brought into the analysis, with the aim of describing an extensive pattern
163 of MU implementation and opportunities across Europe.
164

165 **2.2 Multi-use analysis in the case studies**

166 The same approach and steps of analysis (Fig. 2) were used in all case studies to ensure comparability.
167 Desk analysis and stakeholder engagement were applied iteratively along the analysis process, with
168 initial feedback from stakeholders activating additional desk research and final feedback from
169 stakeholders collected at the end of the process.

170

171 **Fig. 2 Scheme of the methodology used to analyse MU in the case studies.**

172 Desk analysis

173 The desk analysis was aimed at identifying (i) the most suitable MU combinations in the selected local
 174 contexts, (ii) the relevant factors for MU development (RI-1 and RI-2) and (iii) actions needed to support
 175 MU development in the site-specific contexts (RI-4). For each case study, documents and literature
 176 related to MU were identified and screened, such as policies, strategies, laws, regulations, administrative
 177 procedures, plans, strategic environmental assessments (SEAs), environmental impact assessments
 178 (EIAs), feasibility studies, and past and present relevant national and international projects.

179 As a result, the MU combinations potentially relevant for each site, their current status, and perspectives
 180 for development, were identified.

181 The same sources were assessed to prepare preliminary catalogues of the factors used as a basis for
 182 discussion with stakeholders during the stakeholder engagement process, and to analyse MU Potential
 183 (estimation of the degree of opportunity to develop or strengthen the MU) and MU Effect (balance of

184pros and cons of developing the MU) of each combination of uses. These factors are grouped into
185Drivers, Barriers, Added Values, and Impacts (DABI), according to the definitions provided above.
186Finally, a preliminary list of actions needed to support MU development was prepared.

187 *Stakeholder engagement*

188Based on preliminary results from the desk analysis, identification of MU combinations, relevant factors
189for MU development, and actions needed to support MU development (RI-1, RI-2, RI-4) were further
190researched through stakeholder engagement, including interviews, workshops, and focus groups. The
191MU combinations preliminarily identified in each case were discussed with the stakeholder, selected and
192validated through their expert opinion. The preliminary DABI catalogues were evaluated, corrected, and
193the factors included were scored by stakeholders. Experts and stakeholders were also asked to identify
194additional factors according to their knowledge/experience, which were also included in the final DABI
195catalogue. For each DABI group, factors were further grouped into several categories, including e.g.
196economic, social, policy and legal, and technological.
197Finally, preliminary list of actions to promote MU development was discussed with stakeholders and
198their input was used to update the list.

199In order to provide an evaluation of MU Potential and MU Effect on the environmental-socio-economic
200system of the studied areas and to identify the most relevant factors for MU development (RI-2), a
201scoring system was defined for DABI factors and quantitative definitions of MU Potential and MU Effect
202were introduced (Tab. 1 and Tab. 2).

203

204 **Tab. 1. Scoring system for Drivers and Barriers and definition of MU Potential.**

<p>Steps to undertake in order to evaluate MU Potential:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • scoring of drivers by each stakeholder • calculation of the average of Drivers scores • scoring of Barriers by each stakeholder • calculation of the average of Barriers scores • MU Potential estimation. 	
<p>Scoring of Drivers: a positive sign is attributed to factors supporting MU according to the following scale:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • high priority score = +3 • medium priority score = +2 • low priority score = +1 • not relevant¹ score = 0 • absent² score = 0 • I do not know³ no score is given 	<p>Scoring of Barriers: a negative sign is attributed to factors hindering MU development according to the following scale:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • high obstacle score = -3 • medium obstacle score = -2 • low obstacle score = -1 • not relevant¹ score = 0 • absent² score = 0 • I do not know³ no score is given
<p>MU Potential is evaluated by averaging the average of Drivers scores and the average of Barriers scores. MU Potential can assume values in the interval [-1.5, 1.5]⁴, where -1.5 reflects an absolute negative MU Potential and 1.5 an absolute positive MU Potential. A value of 0 for MU Potential can occur when there is a balance between factors promoting MU development and factors hindering it. The development/strengthening of MU will therefore depend upon which of them will prevail. The knowledge of positive and negative factors is useful to address actions aimed at facilitating MU development.</p>	
<p>Notes</p> <p>¹ The factor is present, but it has no influence on MU Potential or MU Effect.</p> <p>² The factor is not present.</p> <p>³ There is no knowledge about the factor</p> <p>⁴ The negative extreme -1.5 is calculated by applying a score of -3 to all Barriers (B) and a score of 0 to all Drivers (D), calculating their averages, respectively (average of B = -3; average of D = 0), and finally calculating the average of these averages which is -1.5. The reverse process is applied for the positive extreme +1.5, where all Drivers were scored 3 and all Barriers were scored 0, and the average of the sum of their averages is +1.5 [26]</p>	

205

206 **Tab. 2. Scoring system for Added values and Impacts and definition of MU Effect.**

<p>Steps to undertake in order to evaluate MU Effect:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • scoring of Added values by each stakeholder • calculation of average of Added values scores • scoring of Impacts by each stakeholder • calculation of average of Impacts scores MU Effect estimation. 	
<p>Scoring of Added Values: a positive sign is attributed to factors representing benefits of developing or reinforcing MU and the following scoring scale is applied:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • high added value score = +3 • medium added value score = +2 • low added value score = +1 • not relevant¹ score = 0 • absent² score = 0 • I do not know³ no score is given given 	<p>Scoring of Impacts: a negative sign is attributed to factors representing negative effects of developing or expanding MU and the following scoring scale is applied:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • high impact score = -3 • medium impact score = -2 • low impact score = -1 • not relevant¹ score = 0 • absent² score = 0 • I do not know³ no score is given given
<p>MU Effect is evaluated by averaging the average Added values score and the average Impacts score. MU Effect can assume values in the interval [-1.5, 1.5]⁴, where -1.5 reflects an absolute negative MU Effect and 1.5 an absolute positive MU Effect. The case of MU Effect = 0 can occur where there is a balance between pros and cons of MU development. The knowledge of positive and negative factors is very useful to address actions aimed at maximising the added value of MU.</p>	
<p>Notes</p> <p>¹ The factor is present, but it has no influence on MU potential or MU Effect.</p> <p>² The factor is not present.</p> <p>³ There is no knowledge about the factor</p> <p>⁴ The negative extreme -1.5 is calculated by applying a score of -3 to all impacts (I) and a score of 0 to all added values (A), calculating their averages, respectively (average of I = -3; average of A = 0), and finally calculating the average of these averages which is -1.5. The reverse process is applied for the positive extreme +1.5, where all added values scored 3 and all impacts scored 0, and the average of the sum of their averages is +1.5 [25].</p>	

207

208 Stakeholder engagement was performed for individual case studies, whereby local (municipality level,
 209 regional (sub-national level), national level) stakeholders and experts were selected according to their
 210 competences and expertise in each of the sectors involved in a potential MU.

211 A total of 125 stakeholders were engaged through the 10 case studies. Stakeholders included, amongst
 212 others, regulators, licensing competent authorities, commercial sectors (single entrepreneurs or
 213 associations), developers, consultants, academics and representatives from civil organizations.

214 Stakeholders were engaged through interviews, in addition, one focus group was organized for case study
 215 (Sweden) and one workshop was carried out to discuss case study 9 (Italy). Participating stakeholders

216 had the option to comment on more than one MU combination and hence identify factors and score more
 217 than one catalogue, resulting in a total of 171 contributions to DABI catalogues.

218 **Tab. 3. Stakeholders engaged across cases. Stakeholders had the option to comment on more than**
 219 **one MU combination, therefore: total stakeholders = number of persons engaged; total**
 220 **contributions = number of inputs to DABI catalogues (factors identification and scoring).**

Case study	Policy makers & regulators	Commercial sectors	Public-private partnerships	Developers & consultants	Academics & experts	Civil society	Total stakeholders	Total contributions to DABI catalogues
1	-	6	-	-	3	-	9	9
2	5	2	6	5	4	-	22	36
3	1	1	-	1	1	-	4	8
4	5	3	-	2	-	1	11	15
5	3	4	-	-	1	1	9	8
6	5	3	-	-	1	3	12	16
7	2	2	-	2	3	2	11	14
8	3	1	-	5	1	1	11	17
9	5	8	2	1	6	2	24	29
10	5	1	-	1	1	4	12	19

221

222 All participants in the study signed the consent form prepared under the H2020 MUSES project this
 223 study was part of. This consent form was prepared and developed under the Ethical Requirements held in
 224 the Grant Agreement (Work Package 6 of the project) to ensure compliance with EU H2020 funded
 225 projects. The stakeholder consent form and the Informed Consents Procedures Manual that partners have
 226 followed during the course of the study were approved by The Innovation and Networks Executive
 227 Agency (INEA), the funders for MUSES at the beginning of the project.

228 Stakeholders were engaged in a participatory process following a phased approach: primarily they were
 229 contacted via telephone/e-mail and were introduced to the aim of the study, the research already
 230 conducted, and the MUs identified at the case study level. They were invited to be involved in research
 231 for the case study. Upon their acceptance, they were engaged with interviews, workshops, and focus
 232 groups. Where possible, face-to-face interviews were conducted. Alternatively, interviews were
 233 undertaken via videoconferencing facilities; interviews lasted between 1.5-2 hours.

234

2352.3 Data elaboration

236An integrated DABI catalogue was built considering the results from the 10 cases and including all
 237factors identified (about 1000 rows), the scores attributed by stakeholders and several descriptive
 238attributes. Statistics and graphics presented in this publication were computed using Python code and
 239organised in a Jupyter notebook, fully available in [27].

240In order to cluster MU combinations into groups, to be analysed and compared through further analysis,
 241several general characteristics of MU combinations were defined, as described in Tab. 4.

242**Tab. 4. Characteristics used to describe the MU combinations.**

Characteristic	Definition
Driving sector	It is the strongest maritime sector/use of the sea of the combination, from the economic point of view and/or in terms of dimension (e.g. number of activities, number of employees, etc., in the specific case study).
Implementation	Two alternative options are used to define the combination: Potential = no real (actual of past) examples of the combinations are found in the study area but opportunities for its development are identified (including planning and design phase); Implemented = real example of the combination are available for the study area, even in pilot scale, or developed within a project.
Type	Type of infrastructures necessary for the maritime sectors / uses of the sea involved in the combination. Hard uses (H) = uses requiring long-term installation of major infrastructures e.g. offshore wind farms or oil and gas platforms [2]. Soft uses (S) = a mobile and fleeting uses, often requiring less investment and not demanding the realization of large infrastructures e.g. recreation and tourism [2]. Three alternative options are used to define the combination: H&H, H&S, S&S.
Location	Two alternative options are used to define the combination, with reference to the sea area for actual or potential location of MU: Nearshore (N) = approximately <12nm; Offshore (O) = approximately >12 nm.
Innovation	Two alternative options are used to define the combination: Traditional = maritime sector / use of the sea traditionally established in the area, sometimes also linked to local jobs and tradition. New (N) = new maritime sector / use of the sea recently established or in process to be established in the area.
Trends	Two alternative options are used to define the combination: Growing = maritime sector / use of the sea which is presently growing in terms of economic development, dimension; Static = maritime sector / use of the sea which is presently static or declining in terms of economic development, dimension.
Resources	Two alternative options are used to define the combination: Abiotic = the maritime sector / uses of the sea is based on the exploitation of abiotic resource(s); Biotic = the maritime sector / uses of the sea is based on the exploitation of biotic resources.

243

244To MU Potential and MU Effect values computed as indicated above, a coefficient of variation (CV) was
 245associated in order to take into consideration variability of given scores. CV is calculated as the ratio of
 246the standard deviation σ to the mean μ . E.g. in case of the CV related to potential (P), calculated using
 247drivers (D) and barriers (B) scores, the following formula applies:

$$248 CV_p = \left(\frac{\sigma_D}{\mu_D} - \frac{\sigma_B}{\mu_B} \right) / 2$$

249

250 Information gathered during the desk analysis and stakeholder engagement process was compiled and
251 analysed according to the RIs:

- 252 – RI-1: most relevant MU combinations for each case study were identified and described
253 according to the characteristics defined in Tab. 3 (results presented in 4.1).
- 254 – RI-2 and RI-3: MU Potential and MU Effect and DABI results were analysed by (i) combinations
255 (results presented in 4.2) and (ii) by cases (results presented in 4.3)
- 256 – RI-3: MU Potential and MU Effect were analysed by grouping combinations according to some
257 of the general characteristic, namely Location, Type and Driving sector (results presented in 4.4)
- 258 – RI-4: actions recommended to facilitate and promote MU implementation and strengthening were
259 organized in categories, according to the type of action suggested (results presented in 4.5).

260

2614 **Results**

2624.1 **Most suitable MU combinations in specific European locations**

26325 MU combinations were identified in the 10 cases (Tab. 5). Being some of the combinations in
264 common in different cases, a total of 16 different, relevant MU combinations was identified.
265 Combinations were classified according to the characteristics given in Tab. 4 with specific reference to
266 the local context in which the MU was analysed within a given case. Other, less relevant combinations
267 were identified in some of the case studies but were not considered for further analysis due to their
268 comparative immaturity or lack of significant interest from stakeholders.

269Tab. 5. MU combinations identified as relevant in the case studies and their major characteristics. Acronyms used in the table: WI = 270offshore wind energy production; TI = tidal energy production; E = environmental protection; M = environmental monitoring; F = 271fisheries; A = aquaculture; WA = wave energy production; S = shipping; T = tourism; H = underwater cultural heritage; O&G = oil & 272gas decommissioning; R = marine renewable energy production; D = desalination.

	Case Study No.	MU Combination	Driving Sector	Implementation	Type	Location	Innovation	Trends	Resources	No. Drivers	No. Barriers	ValuesNo. Added	No. Impacts	Total)No. Factors
1	1	WI & F	WI	Potential	Hard&Soft	Offshore	Traditional&New	Growing&Static	Abiotic&Biotic	19	17	10	19	65
2	2	TI & E	TI	Potential	Hard&Soft	Nearshore	Traditional&New	Growing&Static	Abiotic&Biotic	9	11	6	17	43
3	2	TI & M	TI	Potential	Hard&Hard	Nearshore	Traditional&New	Growing&Growing	Abiotic&Biotic	8	1	10	0	19
4	3	WI & F	WI	Potential	Hard&Soft	Offshore	Traditional&New	Growing&Static	Abiotic&Biotic	4	4	3	1	12
5	3	WI & A	A	Potential	Hard&Hard	Offshore	New&New	Growing&Growing	Abiotic&Biotic	3	7	3	1	14
6	4	WA & A	WA	Potential	Hard&Hard	Both	New&New	Growing&Growing	Abiotic&Biotic	33	35	23	9	100
7	4	S & R	S	Potential	Hard&Hard	Nearshore	Traditional&New	Growing&Static	Abiotic&Abiotic	24	36	10	6	76
8	5	T & A	T	Implemented	Soft&Soft	Nearshore	Traditional&Trad.	Growing&Growing	Biotic&Biotic	23	24	20	2	69
9	5	T & E	T	Implemented	Soft&Soft	Nearshore	Traditional&Trad	Growing&Static	Biotic&Biotic	12	9	12	4	37
10	5	T & F	T	Implemented	Soft&Soft	Nearshore	Traditional&Trad	Growing&Static	Biotic&Biotic	19	15	13	1	48
11	6	T & F	T	Implemented	Soft&Soft	Nearshore	Traditional&Trad	Growing&Static	Biotic&Biotic	25	17	20	1	36
12	6	T & H & E	T	Implemented	Soft&Soft	Nearshore	Traditional&Trad	Growing&Growing	Abiotic&Abiotic	21	7	13	5	46
13	6	T & E	T	Implemented	Soft&Soft	Both	Traditional&Trad	Growing&Growing	Biotic&Biotic	11	4	6	4	27
14	7	WI & A	WI	Potential	Hard&Soft	Offshore	New&New	Growing&Static	Abiotic&Biotic	8	10	6	5	29
15	7	WI & T	WI	Implemented	Hard&Soft	Offshore	Traditional&New	Growing&Static	Abiotic&Abiotic	8	8	10	5	31
16	8	WI & A	WI	Potential	Hard&Soft	Offshore	New&New	Growing&Growing	Abiotic&Biotic	11	20	11	15	57
17	8	WI & E & T	WI	Potential	Hard&Soft	Offshore	Traditional&Trad	Growing&Static	Abiotic&Biotic	17	24	15	13	69
18	9	T & F	T	Implemented	Soft&Soft	Nearshore	Traditional&Trad	Static&Static	Biotic&Biotic	10	12	10	4	36
19	9	T & A	T	Potential	Soft&Soft	Nearshore	Traditional&Trad	Static&Static	Biotic&Biotic	9	10	9	4	32
20	9	T & E	T	Potential	Soft&Soft	Nearshore	Traditional&Trad	Static&Static	Biotic&Biotic	9	13	9	4	35
21	9	T & H	T	Potential	Soft&Soft	Nearshore	Traditional&Trad	Static&Static	Abiotic&Abiotic	10	10	5	4	29
22	9	O&G & T & A	O&G dec.	Potential	Hard&Soft	Offshore	Traditional&New	Growing&Static	Abiotic&Biotic	10	22	42	7	51
23	9	O&G & R	O&G dec.	Potential	Hard&Hard	Offshore	Traditional&New	Growing&Static	Abiotic&Abiotic	7	24	15	8	54
24	10	R & D	R	Potential	Hard&Hard	Offshore	New&New	Growing&Growing	Abiotic&Abiotic	8	15	13	0	36
25	10	T & F	T	Implemented	Soft&Soft	Nearshore	Traditional&Trad	Growing&Static	Biotic&Biotic	8	7	12	0	27

273Amongst the 16 different MUs identified, four are currently implemented and 12 have potential to be
274developed in the future in the specific sites. Most MUs involve two sectors (i.e. combination of
275sectors/users) (MU pairs), while remaining three combinations envisage synergies among three different
276sectors in the same marine space (MU triplets). Seven combinations are to be located offshore, seven
277nearshore, and two in both contexts. A high degree of heterogeneity and local specificity in terms of
278combinations is shown across the case studies, with 11 combinations identified in only one case study
279and five combinations identified as relevant for more than one case study. A total of 13 maritime sectors
280were considered in the MU combinations, with tourism, aquaculture and OWE showing a higher
281propensity towards accommodating MU, being identified in a larger number of combinations. Tourism,
282aquaculture and fisheries, followed by environmental protection and OWE, were the sectors considered
283by a greater number of case studies. Renewable energy production at sea - either addressing a specific
284source (wind, wave, or tide) or interpreted collectively - is considered in 10 of the 16 combinations
285explored.

286A total of 25 DABI catalogues were compiled across the 10 case studies, with 23 being scored (only the
287two catalogues for the combinations with O&G decommissioning in case study 9 were not scored). Each
288catalogue consists of four tables, one for each DABI group. The overall DABI catalogue for all the 16
289MU combinations is fully and openly available in [28].

290

291**4.2 MU analyzed across combinations (MU Potential, MU Effect and** 292**DABI)**

293**4.2.1 MU Potential and Effect**

294When comparing MU Potential for the various combinations (Fig. 3 - left), we note that approximately
295half of the combinations are associated with a positive value for MU Potential and the other half
296negative.

297

298**Figure 3. Average MU Potential and MU Effect for combinations and total number of DABI**
 299**factors identified by stakeholders.**

300

301The combinations with the highest MU Potential are TI&M (0.27), T&E&H (0.24) and R&D (0.14).

302However, the tendency for values to score very close to 0, ranging between - 0.3 and +0.3. Such results

303are determined by a balance between the average score of Drivers and Barriers provided by stakeholders'

304opinions. For all combinations, these two elements of factors are both scored quite high (average score of

305Drivers: 0.4 - 2.5; average score of Barriers: -0.7 - -2.5). The generally high average Driver scores

306suggest that interviewed stakeholders perceive there to be opportunities for MU development. Removing

307or decreasing the main Barriers can lead to the creation of conditions favourable for the development of

308MU. The values of the CV show a variability of the average of MU Potential around or below 30% for

309most combinations. Instead, MU Potential for WI&T and WI&A is associated with high values of CV,

310derived from very heterogeneous scores assigned by stakeholders, affecting the significance of average

311MU Potential estimation.

312MU Effect analysis reveals more homogeneity and was mostly estimated as positive by stakeholders
313(Fig. 3 - right), with only two combinations (WI&E&T, S&R) having negative impacts prevailing over
314Added Values. MU Effect ranges from -0.2 to 1.1, assuming values higher than those associated to MU
315Potential. The combinations showing the highest MU Effect are R&D (1.14) and TI&M (1.06), also
316scoring among the highest for MU Potential. In fact, all combinations with positive MU Potential show
317also positive MU Effect, demonstrating coherence in the method and response by stakeholders. Average
318score of Added Values and Impacts got similar range (respectively 0.4 - 2. and -0.34 - -2.6) but with the
319prevalence of Added Values.

320For MU Effect, the values of CV show a higher variability, with values around or below 40% for most of
321combinations. As for MU Potential, MU Effect for WI&T and WI&A is associated with high values of
322CV, significantly affecting the estimation of average MU Effect.

323Despite the balance between Drivers and Barriers identified in all combinations, there seems to be a
324common agreement between stakeholders to consider MU as beneficial, if or when it is implemented,
325with Added Values prevailing over Impacts.

326

3274.2.2 DABI analysis

328Results of the scored DABI catalogues are represented in Figure 4, depicting the average Driver, Barrier,
329Added Value and Impact scores per combination.

330

331Fig. 4. Average scores according to stakeholders for different categories of (a) Drivers, (b) Barriers,
 332(c) Added Values, and (d) Impacts across all combinations.

333 Different categories of **Barriers** are scored similarly (Fig. 4 (b), for example, Technical and Economic
334 barriers average score was -2.1 and 1; Policy & Legal, Administrative, and Social Barriers average score
335 was -1.9). Differences can be identified among combinations: Administrative barriers are particularly
336 relevant for R&D and for the combinations with tourism (concessions of permits, licence limit and
337 complex bureaucratic procedures). For example, in case studies 5 and 9, the lack of a common regulation
338 at national levels for aquaculture-related tourism activities and restrictive rules concerning the number of
339 people hosted aboard aquaculture vessels, and/or hygiene and security constraints, were highlighted as
340 relevant barriers for T&A.

341 Barriers related to social acceptance are relevant for some of the combinations involving aquaculture
342 (WI&A, WA&A) due to limitations concerning cooperation and dialogue among sectors, public
343 awareness, and limited knowledge of cumulative environmental impacts of the combination; the same
344 can be said for T&E and T&H. In the latter case, social acceptance of these MUs are in part related to
345 environmental concerns: for example, resistance of UCH authorities and environmental non-
346 governmental organizations (NGOs) due to fear of looting/damage of artefacts and damage of natural
347 ecosystems.

348 Generally, the combination most limited by barriers is S&R (average score = -2.54), followed by T&H (-
349 2.35) and WA&A (-2.2), while the less impacted are W&T (-0.68), followed by WI&E&T (-1.70) and
350 TI&M (-1.73).

351 According to stakeholders, almost all combinations are associated to Economic, Environmental and
352 **Social Added Values** with a comparable average score of 2.0-2.1 (Fig. 4 - c). Technical Added Values
353 are particularly relevant for S&R (e.g. in case study 4, MU can provide availability of proof of concept
354 upon which more effective and cheaper global solutions can be based); benefits concerning risk
355 management and safety are envisaged from the combination of T&A (e.g. in case study 5, MU can
356 provide sharing of responsibilities and safety-related costs); Environmental Added Values are foreseen
357 for S&R (e.g. in case study 4, MU can provide a reduction in green-house gas (GHG) emissions where

358shipping terminals tend to be emission hot spots), R&D (e. g. in case study 10, MU can provide a low-
359carbon footprint of energy/water supply), TI&E (e.g. in case study 2, in addition to reduction of GHG
360emissions, turbine supports may create artificial reefs and the overall areas will likely act as no-fishing
361zones).

362Numerous Added Values are expected from the implementation of the T&F combinations: Economic
363Added Values, since pescatourism can produce an additional income for fishers due to the development
364of new market opportunities and sector diversification, as well as benefits for the local economy, through
365an expected increase of commercialisation of local fish products; Social Added Values are expected for
366this combination since case studies recognized a general professional growth of operators involved in
367pescatourism, with the improvement of personal skills and management capacity. Educative benefits for
368tourists and civil society are also expected, with an increased awareness about the issues of the marine
369environment and fisheries. In case studies 5, 6, 9 and 10, Environmental Added Values include the
370possible contribution of pescatourism to the sustainable management of fisheries and the relief from
371coastal tourism pressures.

372From a general perspective, the combinations that seem to have more benefits (higher Added value) to
373provide are T&E (average score = 2.42), T&A (2.31), S&R (2.30), followed by R&D (2,27), T&F (2.19)
374and T&H (2.1).

375

376**4.3 MU analyzed across case studies (MU Potential, MU Effect and DABI)**

377**4.3.1 MU Potential and Effect**

378MU Potential shows positive values in half of the case studies and negative values in the other half, with
379all results close to 0 (Fig. 5).

380

381**Fig. 5. Average MU Potential and MU Effect provided by stakeholder perception in the 10 case**
 382**studies (results from all combinations considered in each case are averaged together), and total**
 383**number of DABI factors identified by stakeholders.**

384

385The highest potential for MU is apparent in case study 3 (in Germany), considering the potential
 386development of MU between WI&F and WI&A in the German EEZ; followed by case study 6 (in
 387Portugal), considering the potential development of tourism driven MUs (T&E, T&F, T&H&E) in the
 388Azores, and by case study 2 (in Scotland), considering the potential development of tidal energy driven
 389combinations (TI&E, TI&M) in North Scotland. The CV associated to MU Potential in these three cases
 390ranges between 25-35%, demonstrating general agreement in the scores expressed by stakeholders. The
 391cases with the lowest MU Potential are case study 8 (Denmark), considering the potential development of

392MU between WI&A and WI&A&T; followed by case study 7 (Sweden), considering WI&A and WI&T,
393and case study 9 (Italy), considering four combinations with tourism: T&F, T&A, T&E, T&H. Case
394study 7 shows a very high CV (70%), indicating great disagreement in the scores attributed by different
395stakeholders.

396All cases with positive MU Potential show positive MU Effect as well; also some of the cases indicating
397negative MU Potential values are associated to positive values for MU Effect (case 5, 7, 9),
398demonstrating stakeholder's positive expectations for MU development. Eight cases in total show
399positive MU Effect and the other two show results very close to 0. The highest estimated MU Effect is
400associated to case 10 (Greece) with two different MUs were considered (R&D, T&F).

401

4024.3.2 DABI analysis

403Results of the scored DABI catalogues are represented in Fig. 6.

404

405

406 Fig. 6. Average scores according to stakeholders for different categories of (a) Drivers, (b)

407 Barriers, (c) Added Values, and (d) Impacts across cases.

408As for **Barriers** (Fig. 6b), average scores of different categories are relatively similar, such as Economic
409(-2.12), Risk & Safety (2.1) and Environmental (2.01). Despite this, the distribution across cases
410highlights some specificities. Differences in the importance of Administrative barriers can be
411highlighted: they are very relevant for case study 5 (3.0), and relevant for case studies 9 (-2.5), 1 (-2.2)
412and 10 (-2.2). Barriers include for example, factors like the complexity of licensing procedure in T&A
413and T&F, or the lack of coordination between institutions involved in T&E and T&H. This demonstrated
414the role of local context in determining conditions favourable to MU.

415Technical barriers show heterogeneity of scoring across cases in relation with the specific MU
416combinations, with the highest values related to case study 4 (e.g. difficulties in OWE transmission and
417storage in ports; lack of available infrastructure for Shore Side Electricity (SSE) in ports; impracticable to
418convert some type of vessels like tankers and cargo to new powering systems), and case study 1 (e.g.
419incompatibility of OWE components with fishing operations and vice versa; fishing vessels and gears not
420compatible with altered sea conditions due to OWE).

421Conversely, Economic and Social barriers show a more homogeneous distribution across the cases.

422Considering **Added Values** (Fig. 6c), economic benefits are expected particularly in case studies 5, 6,
423and 9, deriving from the implementation of tourism-driven combinations (e.g. increase of revenues at
424local levels, cost reduction, diversification of tourism sector). Environmental Added Values from MU
425implementation are expected across all cases. The same pattern exist for Social Added Values with the
426highest scores identified in case study 3 (Germany) (e.g. leaving free space at sea by combining uses
427would benefit communities in the long run), case study 1 (North Scotland) (e.g. MU promoting longevity
428of fisheries sector; boosting innovation in the sector, increase trust of fishermen; benefit the local
429communities at large), and case study 5 (in the Algarve, Portugal) (e.g. opportunities for business at
430family level; conservation of traditional activity and their culture; promotion of sea-food healthy diet).

431

432

433**4.4 Analysis of MU by type of combination**

434In order to provide a general understanding on what types of MU are seen as more promising across
435European Seas, average MU Potential and Effect of different groups of combinations were compared
436(Fig.7) based on some of the MU characteristics identified in Table 4: MU location (Nearshore vs
437Offshore), MU type (Hard uses vs Soft uses), and MU driving sector (renewables-driven MU vs tourism-
438driven MU).

Average Potential and Effect scores per nearshore or offshore combinations

Average Potential and Effect scores per Hard or Soft cases/combinations

Average Potential and Effect scores per Renewable- and Tourism-driven combinations

439

440**Figure 7. Comparison of MU Potential and MU Effect between different characteristics of**
 441**combinations: (a) Nearshore vs Offshore, (b) Hard vs Soft, and (c) Renewables-driven vs Tourism-**
 442**driven.**

443 Considering the location of the MU (Fig. 7a), both groups show MU Potential values close to 0. The
444 average Potential for “Nearshore” combinations is slightly positive while the one for "Offshore"
445 combinations is slightly negative, suggesting the offshore environment is more difficult to be approached
446 by two or more combined uses. Furthermore, this may also suggest that effective spatial management has
447 greater demand in nearshore environments where there is greater competition, and thus MU is viewed
448 more positively closer to shore. Additionally, both show positive values of MU Effect, with "Nearshore"
449 combinations associated to higher values of MU Effect.

450 In what concerns the type of MU (Fig. 7b), values are low for both “Hard&Hard” and “Soft&Soft” MU.
451 Nevertheless MU Potential of combinations considering two hard uses are about three times higher than
452 the one involving two soft sectors. This can be explained by hard sectors (e.g. renewable energy
453 producers, large-scale aquaculture operators, utilising engineering infrastructures at sea) being considered
454 by stakeholders more prepared than soft sectors (e.g. tourism, environmental protection) to face
455 challenges involving combinations of different uses: technological changes, economic investments,
456 administrative processes, etc. The lowest MU Potential is obtained by combinations considering both
457 hard and soft uses, where two very different approaches/traditions of the use of the sea have to be
458 combined. It is worth noting that MU Effect results are dissimilar, with the highest values being
459 attributed to the combination of two soft uses (about three times higher than for Hard&Hard). Similarly,
460 combinations with both hard and soft uses obtained higher values of MU Effect than combinations with
461 two hard uses.

462 Finally, the comparison of Renewables-driven with Tourism-driven combinations (Fig. 7c) shows that
463 both groups have positive values of MU Potential, with comparable values, while both show positive MU
464 Effect scores, with the Tourism-driven group prevailing by a factor of about two.

465

466 **4.5 Key actions to be undertaken to promote MU development**

467 Results from desk analysis and the stakeholder engagement processes in case studies allowed the
468 compilation of a set of recommended actions (Supporting Information Tab. S1) to promote the
469 implementation or the strengthening of MU. The most relevant recommendations are summarized in 10
470 themes:

- 471 **— Policy, strategies, and planning.** 10 of the 16 MU combinations analysed referenced the
472 need to promote and incorporate MU in the MSP process. MU concepts can be promoted
473 through identification of zones suitable for MU, by assigning preferences towards MU versus
474 single uses (e.g. OWE), ensuring appropriate representation of stakeholders, etc. marin
475 renewable energy (MRE) combinations have placed greater emphasis on GHG emissions
476 reduction targets on EU, national, and local levels in order to demonstrate the benefits of co-
477 location and uptake for climate change agendas. Furthermore, the majority of MU
478 combinations including tourism (4/7) have referenced the need to create and/or improve
479 regional sectoral policies focused on removing barriers to these MUs and targeting cross-
480 sector needs and opportunities.
- 481 **— Legal framework and administrative issues.** MU combinations which address these issues
482 are those which are either driven by tourism or OWE in the North and Baltic Seas. The need
483 for more consistent legal and administrative framework for MU at national and sub-national
484 levels was identified, e.g the need to harmonize safety legislation for pesca-tourism .
- 485 **— Funding.** The implementation of a government subsidy in order to make MRE more
486 competitive in the electricity generation market, thereby enhancing their commercial and
487 economic viability, was indicated. Given the pre-commercial status of MRE technology in
488 relation to other uses of the sea, these subsidies play an essential role in allowing for the
489 implementation of MRE with any other use [17].

- 490 — **Research and data production.** OWE combinations emphasized the promotion of data
491 sharing protocols for health and safety considerations (e.g. fishing within OWE areas), and to
492 disseminate environmental baseline data, which may provide a greater knowledge base for
493 environmental sectors, help obtain public understanding and acceptance, and provide
494 knowledge transfer amongst technology and project developers [16]. Moreover, in-depth
495 assessments of the cumulative economic, social and environmental impacts of different MU
496 combinations (including the tourism-driven ones), and proof-of-concept and business models,
497 are required in order to encourage financial investment.
- 498 — **Technical improvements and innovation.** The tourism-driven combinations (T&F, T&A,
499 T&E, T&H) recommend that the best type of boats for developing MU be identified,
500 accomplishing requirements from commercial sectors and the need to host tourists on board.
501 Some renewables combinations located in the Eastern Atlantic and Baltic Sea target the need
502 for the performance of particular innovative studies: on moorings, cable installation, fishing-
503 friendly cable protection, connection of offshore energy to ports and on shore-side electricity
504 (SSE), etc.
- 505 — **Pilot projects.** The need for promoting pilot projects and testing sites in order to enhance the
506 general knowledge base and remove social barriers was identified, with OWE combinations in
507 the North Sea specifically adding that small-scale pilot projects should be exempt from full-
508 scale assessments.
- 509 — **Networks and clusters.** It is suggested that a joint and cohesive approach to developing and
510 strengthening MU is required on EU, national, and local levels, whereby multi-sectoral and
511 transdisciplinary actors can work together to overcome barriers and exploit mutual benefits
- 512 — **Dialogue and cooperation.** The need for dialogue and active cooperation resulted from the
513 most diverse and numerous recommendations across cases and combinations. Tourism-driven

514 combinations aim for the facilitation of dialogue between regulators/policy makers, academia
515 and industry/commercial sectors, and amongst different sectors (e.g. to develop project ideas
516 to pilot/implement MU through already available opportunities). Knowledge exchange on MU
517 practices was identified as a need, as well as integration and coordination both horizontally
518 (between different sectors) and vertically (across governance levels, from EU to local). In the
519 case of W&F in the North Sea, there is specific reference to the need for a cross-border
520 exchange with regulators of bordering countries where this combination exists already (i.e.
521 UK, DK) in order to find commonalities and streamline management approaches.

522 **— Education and training.** The most frequently cited recommendation from the cases
523 considering combinations with tourism was the promotion of education to sector operators. In
524 addition, T&F, T&E, T&A also highlighted the need for training and capacity building for
525 sector operators. MRE combinations located in the Eastern Atlantic also demonstrated a
526 theme of advocating for local stakeholder involvement in participatory planning and decision-
527 making processes, which in turn would ideally resolve issues of local residents and
528 communities objecting to MRE developments, potentially due to mistrust in decision-makers
529 [29].

530 **— Communication and social awareness.** The most commonly cited recommendation across
531 cases and combinations was to promote the culture of the sea, including seamanship tradition,
532 expertise, professions, historical marine routes, etc., which occurred for all tourism-driven
533 combinations (T&F, T&A, T&E, T&H). This recommendation is underpinned by the need to
534 promote and market MU and its benefits, including the involvement of social media, to spread
535 the MU concept, and to favour data access. The most prevalent recommendations for
536 renewables-based MU combinations target the engagement of local stakeholders for effective
537 dissemination of results and existing knowledge. This theme may be in line with the
538 Education and Training, whereby the involvement and empowerment of local communities in

539 renewable energy development projects, particularly marine developments which suffer from
540 greater unknowns concerning environmental, social, and economic impacts relative to onshore
541 technologies and developments [30], is essential in order to secure community buy-in and
542 facilitate project implementation [31].

543

544 **5 Discussion**

545 **5.1 On the methods used and their influence on results**

546 Some methodological limitations, mainly due to characteristics of data collected, should be
547 acknowledged when comparing the results of different case studies. Heterogeneity of data types is an
548 issue, as available data derived from different steps of the methodology are either qualitative (e.g.
549 identification of DABI factors) or quantitative (scores attributed to DABI factors). Concerning the latter,
550 scores represent an individual quantification of DABI factors, influenced by stakeholders' opinion,
551 knowledge and experience, so that a certain degree of subjectivity is included in the scoring process. This
552 must be taken into account in the evaluation of results, their integration and interpretation. Moreover,
553 scoring methodology and the formulas adopted to estimate MU Potential and MU Effect could also be a
554 possible source of uncertainty. For example, the average Driver and Barrier scores are not responsive to
555 differences in the total number of drivers and/or barriers identified. If both DABI groups have a
556 substantially different number of factors they would weigh the same regardless in the MU Potential
557 calculation. In addition, heterogeneity across case studies should be considered, such as the number of
558 interviews performed and number of factors included in the DABI catalogues. Furthermore, when
559 aggregating results from case studies, for example by combination, the number of available data (e.g.
560 scored DABI factors) may vary, since the various cases undertook different numbers of interviews.
561 Variability of scores across cases was considered by introducing the CV, used to provide an estimation of
562 the degree of confidence associated to the values of MU Potential and MU Effect.

563When considering the possible extension of the methodology to other contexts, some considerations
564should be take into account: the overall low score for MU Potential is most likely linked to the low
565degree of implementation of MU in the case study areas we considered (and, at present, in EU seas in
566general [31]). Most cases considered potential MU combinations, with only some examples of real
567application which still need to be widened and strengthened. In addition, given that these values are
568assigned by stakeholder perceptions, there might be a general tendency to balance pros and cons of new
569opportunities. In addition, the predominately positive score for MU Effect may have emerged by the
570general tendency of stakeholders to envisage the benefits of a new—and poorly known—approach to the
571use of the sea, instead of the negative impacts. Again, this may be related to the limited experience of
572MU implementation in EU seas (e.g. deployed pilots).

573Moreover, it is worth noting that the total number of factors included in the DABI catalogues (Drivers,
574Barriers, Added Values, and Impacts), identified and revised by stakeholders, provides an indication of
575the degree of knowledge (level of detail) that stakeholders hold for the different combinations, and is also
576related to the state of implementation and experiences available for individual MUs.

577Despite these constraints, the methodology applied allowed to provide additional understanding about the
578RIs identified at the beginning of the study and is readily transferable to different European locations and
579marine management areas in other parts of the world outside Europe, supporting who are seeking to
580determine the state of knowledge of MU and target certain combinations for strengthening and
581development on micro and macro-economic scales.

582

583**5.2 MU combinations with more opportunity to be developed**

584The aim of the study was to provide knowledge on which MU combinations have a greater opportunity to
585be developed and/or strengthened, and what are seen as more beneficial for environmental and socio-
586economic contexts. As demonstrated by the results of the analysis, the MU combinations with the
587greatest potential for development or strengthening, and subsequently those which have received a

588 positive MU Potential score (Fig. 3) are those driven by renewable energy (TI&M; R&D; TI&E; WI&F),
589 along with those driven by tourism (T&E&H; T&E). For renewables, it is noteworthy to mention that 3/4
590 of the combinations with highest score were those which did not specifically focus on OWE as the only
591 form of renewable energy being analysed. Often times with OWE combinations, barriers were cited
592 concerning the lack of MU in MSP, complicated licensing processes, and a lack of cross-sectoral
593 communication. Conversely, the two tidal energy combinations obtained positive MU Potential scores,
594 suggesting that this form of renewable energy production may be better suited to accommodate MU, and/
595 or have greater benefits via implementation. This, however, is more speculative than conclusions drawn
596 from OWE, given that tidal energy is relatively immature while OWE has obtained commercial status
597 globally [17]. Furthermore, OWE combinations were all located offshore (Tab.2), whereby 3/4 of the
598 highest scoring renewable energy combinations (TI&M; R&D; TI&E) were located nearshore, which
599 suggests that the distance from shore of renewables acts as an indicator towards the difficulty of MU
600 implementation. In fact, this is evident also when considering all combinations, as shown in Fig. 7 (Top).
601 The only OWE combination scored positively for MU Potential was the OWE and Fisheries, located in
602 the North Sea, off the East Coast of Scotland (case studies 1 and 4). This locational theme of successful
603 renewables-based combinations is further supported by the fact that all renewables which did score well
604 were located off the coasts of Scotland, suggesting that the strong MSP processes and marine renewable
605 energy policies and legislation in place are a key factor towards the success of MU implementation,
606 specifically concerning renewable energy.

607 Another theme which separates the higher scored renewables combinations from stand-alone OWE
608 combinations is the type of use that they are paired with, as the two highest scored renewables
609 combinations (TI&M; R&D) were paired with other hard uses, whereas all OWE combinations were
610 paired with soft uses (Tab. 5), suggesting that there is either greater potential in facilitating MU with
611 significant infrastructure, or that the MU combinations are more viably co-located when they are of the
612 same type of use (i.e. hard & hard, soft & soft). Again, this evidence is also shown when considering all

613 combinations together (Fig. 7b). An extension of the above pattern is the high potential of combinations
614 of uses which are both abiotic (Tab. 5), whereas 2/3 different types of OWE combinations were paired
615 with biotic uses (WI&A; WI&E&T), suggesting that the co-existence of renewables with other MU
616 exploring non-living resources is more practical than co-existence with MU exploring living resources.
617 Regarding combinations with renewables, factors such as growing and/or static, traditional and/or new,
618 or having potential or being in-place (Tab. 5), do not seem to demonstrate a consistent relationship
619 towards successful high MU Potential combinations in comparison to the less favourably scored OWE
620 combinations.

621 When viewing the opportunities for renewables-based MU combinations emanating from average driver
622 scores (Fig. 8 - Top), as well as combinations which demonstrate the greatest benefits if implemented
623 emanating from average added value scores (Fig. 8- Bottom), many of the themes which are prevalent for
624 MU Potential scores are further strengthened.

625

626 **Figure 8. Comparison of MU Combinations: (Top) ranked by Drivers – highest to lowest, and**
 627 **(Bottom) ranked by Added Values – highest to lowest.**

628

629 R&D, S&R, and TI&M demonstrate the greatest driver and added value scores. All of these
 630 combinations are located off the coasts of Scotland, and none of which focus on OWE solely. As
 631 mentioned previously, all OWE combinations are located offshore, whereby 2/3 of the highest scoring
 632 renewable energy combinations (S&R; TI&M) are located nearshore, and are paired with other ‘hard’,
 633 abiotic uses. An analysis of the highest scored drivers for each of these three combinations do not,
 634 however, demonstrate any clear thematic consistencies either for individual factors or categories. Thus,

635no synergistic conclusions can be drawn from this analysis towards renewables-based MU drivers in
636general, even though the three combinations in question are all located within Scottish jurisdiction.
637Rather, the lack of commonalities amongst drivers and added values would suggest that each renewable
638energy type, and each use in which it is paired with, must be analysed specifically within the context in
639which MU implementation is desired, whereby local site conditions may have the greatest impact on
640successful implementation as opposed to general policy, technical, environmental, or other regional and
641geographical considerations.

642

643For tourism-driven combinations, the combinations paired with UCH and environmental protection were
644the only attributed with positive MU Potential scores. All of these paired uses are categorized as ‘soft’
645uses, with the two tourism-paired combinations including OWE, either on its own or in combination with
646other uses (WI&E&T), receiving the lowest MU Potential scores. This suggests that there is either
647greater potential in facilitating MU with other ‘soft’ uses, or rather that the MU combinations are more
648viable co-located when there are of the same type of use (i.e. hard & hard; soft & soft), as also indicated
649by the results obtained when considering all combinations together (Fig. 7 - Bottom). These
650combinations with high scoring of MU Potential are also combinations where tourism is the driving use
651for the MU, as opposed to OWE being the driving use when combined with tourism, which may suggest
652that tourism is more viable for MU implementation when the demand for touristic activities is the
653primary use as applicable to the geographical region of MU implementation. This connection also has a
654geographical element, as lower-scoring OWE and tourism combinations are both located in the Baltic
655Sea, where there is a greater emphasis on renewables production [32], while higher-scoring tourism with
656soft uses are located in the Eastern Atlantic and the Mediterranean, where tourism is the greater
657economic driver in the regions. Furthermore, all tourism combinations with soft uses are located
658nearshore, whereas the comparatively lowest-scored tourism combinations with OWE are located

659 offshore, which is in-line with the relationships suggested for renewables combinations whereby the
660 distance from shore of renewables acts as an indicator towards the difficulty of MU implementation.

661 An additional element is that 3/4 highest-scored MU Potential tourism combinations are a pairing of
662 traditional uses, whereas pairing tourism with the relatively new uses such as OWE received lower
663 scores. This may suggest that, given certain factors intrinsic to touristic activities, which inherently focus
664 on the health and safety of the tourists, particularly in the marine environment, MU with tourism is more
665 viable when it is paired with a traditional use whereby the risks associated with passenger health and
666 safety are better understood. Regarding tourism combinations, factors such as growing and/or static, or
667 having potential or being in-place, do not seem to demonstrate a consistent relationship towards
668 successful high MU Potential combinations.

669 When viewing the opportunities for tourism-based MU combinations resulting from average Driver
670 scores, all of the themes which are prevalent for MU Potential scores are further strengthened, as
671 T&E&H, T&E, and T&H received the highest scores. An analysis of the highest scored Drivers for each
672 of these three combinations, occurring in the Eastern Atlantic and the Mediterranean, follow the theme of
673 the exploitation of viable marine space in a sustainable manner (i.e. while conserving MPAs and UCH
674 sites) in order to further the economic gain attainable by the expansion and diversification of touristic
675 activities. National legislation and regulations concerning conservation management are also uniformly
676 scored high across all case studies. When considering tourism-based MU combinations, which would
677 obtain the greatest benefits if implemented resulting from average Added Value scores, in addition to the
678 three combinations discussed above, T&A and T&F are also highly scored. Along with the former
679 combinations, T&A and T&F are also concentrated in the Eastern Atlantic and Mediterranean, with
680 tourism being the driving sector for MU implementation, combined with soft uses which are for the most
681 part traditional and biotic, with factors such as growing and/or static, or having potential, or being in-
682 place, not seeming to demonstrate a consistent relationship towards benefits. An examination of the
683 highest scored added values for each of these five combinations demonstrates several common themes.

684 Nearly all combinations referenced economic gain, particularly at the local level, through both increased
685 jobs and the diversification of tourism offer, as amongst the highest scored benefits of MU
686 implementation. Most of the combinations also referenced one form of protection and conservation,
687 whether it be environmental and/or cultural, accompanied by an increased awareness of sectoral cultural
688 operations.

689

690 **5.3 Addressing MU development**

691 Renewables and tourism-driven combinations are highlighted by having the highest potential for MU
692 implementation and benefits provision. In order to facilitate MU development and strengthening in the
693 near-future, it is reasonable that MU be developed around these uses. However, there is a geographical
694 caveat, whereby renewables-based combinations are more successful in the North Sea and Baltic Sea,
695 and thus should be the focus of MU development in those sea basins, whereas tourism-based
696 combinations are more successful in the Eastern Atlantic and Mediterranean Sea, and thus should be the
697 focus of MU development in those sea basins. In order to develop renewables-based combinations in the
698 near-term, renewables infrastructure should be paired with other hard, abiotic uses, while tourism-based
699 combinations should be paired with other soft uses, either biotic or abiotic. Both renewables and tourism-
700 driven combinations should probably focus near-term MU development on nearshore combinations, as
701 offshore combinations are scored less favourably. While OWE is a driving player in the marine
702 environment, OWE combinations might show greater near-term success the closer they are located to
703 shore. More themes were identified across cases and combinations for tourism-driven MU. Specific to
704 tourism, MU combinations which were paired with traditional uses generally scored higher for successful
705 implementation. MU involving tourism should be combined in the near-term with other mature uses, and
706 thus excludes combinations with renewables.

707In order to facilitate MU development and strengthening in the long-term, a key element to target seems
708to be the amalgamation of the renewables and tourism industries, as the results of the DABI analysis have
709demonstrated that they are the two greatest driving sectors for MU development. To facilitate synergies
710between the two industries, more research should be undertaken to determine the viability for
711compatibility of specific elements of these sectors. For tourism, the greatest drivers are national
712legislation and national and sectoral plans and policies. While these are facilitated in Mediterranean and
713Eastern Atlantic countries, renewable plans and policies would seem to be lagging, despite interest in
714development in those countries, albeit to a lesser extent than for tourism (e.g. tourism in the Italy's
715Adriatic Sea vs. OWE). Given that the highest-scored renewables-driven combinations for MU Potential,
716drivers, and added values are all located off the coasts of Scotland, demonstrating strong renewables
717legislation, targets, and national and sectoral plans and policies [18], the comparative analysis would
718suggest that certain nations which are looking to further develop renewables, and have the potential to
719co-locate them with touristic activities, review the strong renewables-based plans and policies, and tailor
720and apply them as applicable. Similarly, nations who have successfully adopted and implemented strong
721renewables plans and policies, and are looking to diversify their touristic offer in order to inject revenues
722into local communities, subsequently enhancing local job opportunities and economic stimulation, may
723benefit from reviewing and adopting the tourism-based plans and policies of nations which have more
724successfully implemented tourism offerings. Finally, as renewables industry further matures
725technologically, studies should be undertaken to evaluate and quantify the risks to the health and safety
726of marine tourist passengers when integrating tourism with renewables, particularly concerning offshore
727location.

728

7296 **Conclusions**

730The concept of MU of the sea has gained prominence in recent years due in-part to competing claims for
731space, initiating the investigation of suitable management policies and procedures for synergistic uses.
732This paper defined and applied a replicable methodology to analyse the characteristics and potential of
733MU development and strengthening through the implementation of quantitative and qualitative methods
734in site-specific local contexts.

735Results from the aggregate analysis of contrasts and commonalities amongst MUs provide that
736renewables-driven and tourism-driven MU combinations demonstrated the greatest degree of potential
737implementation, with the former having prominence in the North and Baltic Seas, and the latter in the
738Mediterranean and Eastern Atlantic. Generally, synergies are acknowledged between uses which are
739either both soft and biotic, as is the case for tourism-driven MU, or hard and abiotic, as is the case for
740renewables-driven MU, while the highest-scoring combinations in terms of MU Potential are located
741nearshore. Given this, combinations including OWE generally received a lower MU Potential score, as
742there are far more unknowns related to operating in an offshore marine environment, as well as elements
743of difficulty related to construction, investment, risk, and health and safety. However, an analysis of
744Drivers and Added Values suggests that each renewable energy type, and each use in which it is paired
745with, must be analysed specifically within the context in which MU implementation is desired, whereby
746local site conditions may have the greatest impact on successful implementation as opposed to general
747policy, technical, environmental, or other regional and geographical considerations.

748The most commonly cited recommendation across cases and combinations was to promote the culture of
749the sea, including seamanship tradition, expertise, professions, historical marine routes, etc., which
750occurred for all tourism-driven combinations. The most prevalent recommendation for renewables-based
751MU combinations target the engagement of local stakeholders for effective dissemination of results and
752existing knowledge. Both of these recommendations provide insight into the need for education, training,
753communication, and social awareness amongst stakeholders with a vested interest and connect to the
754marine environment, as MU is a growing concept in its early stages of development.

755 Most analysed case studies identified a legal and regulatory framework supporting and enabling MU
756 development and operation as a key component to the future of MU. However, the development and
757 implementation of such frameworks, in Europe and beyond, will require clear guidelines and principles
758 derived from the best available knowledge regarding MU. Overall, the selection/development of the
759 type of MU combination as shown by the cases is very much dependent on local conditions
760 such as space availability, physical conditions etc. As MU develops in the future, policies and
761 legislation can help frame societal drivers on EU, national, and local levels and eliminate barriers, while
762 feasibility studies/pilot projects can help maximize synergies and mitigate negative impacts in order to
763 allow MU to reach its optimum potential.

764

765 **Acknowledgements**

766 This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation
767 programme under grant agreement No 727451. The authors would like to thank all of the stakeholder
768 participants involved in the research and all project partners involved in the MUSES project.

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